

Machine Learning-Driven Attack and Fault Classification in CV-QKD Systems After Anomaly Detection

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Abstract— Misdiagnosing faults as attacks significantly reduce the key-generation uptime of CV-QKD systems. To address this, we characterize attacks and faults in CV-QKD systems and propose an approach for anomaly detection and its classification as faults and attacks in CV-QKD copropagating within dense wavelength division multiplexing (DWDM) systems. The proposed method combines analytical techniques for anomaly detection with a deep neural network (DNN) for accurate classification. This approach minimizes unnecessary system shutdowns and can be seamlessly integrated into SDN-enabled CV-QKD systems. Results demonstrate that traditional classifiers, such as Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB), are insufficient for this task. Instead, the use of a DNN, despite its fourfold increase in prediction time, ensures significantly higher classification accuracy, thereby enhancing system reliability and operational efficiency.

Keywords—Continuous variable quantum key distribution (CV-QKD), machine learning, fault management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum key distribution (QKD) systems inherently detect eavesdroppers (Eve) in the quantum channel (QC) which is used to transmit secure keys between two parties (Alice and Bob). The system automatically shuts down key-generation when a threat is present and detected in QC by monitoring the system degradation. A similar degradation may occur in the presence of some faults. However, shutting down key-generation is not always necessary if the fault is non-critical, and its impact is minimal on the performance degradation. Therefore, distinguishing between faults and attacks could be crucial to ensuring higher key-generation uptime of QKD systems.

This work examines potential faults in a continuous-variable QKD (CV-QKD) systems [1] that may arise from integrating it into a dense wavelength division multiplexing (DWDM) setup [2][3] for flex-grid scenario (channel width is a multiple of 12.5 GHz) [4]. In such a scenario filters play a crucial role. At the transmitter (Tx), filters are typically used

to eliminate amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise before mixing the QC with classical channels (CCs), whereas at the receiver (Rx), they extract the QC from the multiplexed QC and CCs [3]. Any fault in these filters can adversely impact the performance of the CV-QKD system. In this work to emulate filters' malfunctioning we consider two cases: i) shifted filter frequency (SFF) and ii) narrow filter bandwidth (NFB) [5][6]. To emulate attacks, we consider channel tampering attack called power-splitting attack [7]. For this attack, Eve intercepts the quantum signal by splitting it, thereby disturbing the quantum state either to gain information or to produce denial of service [7], thus, reducing uptime of key-generation.

In [5], the authors analyzed faults and classification strategies in CV-QKD-integrated DWDM systems but without distinguishing between attacks and faults, before faults classification. This paper introduces an approach to accurately detect anomalies and differentiates if the anomaly is a fault or an attack by analytical techniques and deep neural network (DNN). We also compare DNN's performance with a simple Gaussian naive bayes (GNB) approach [8]. The evaluation is performed both in terms of prediction accuracy and complexity by monitoring prediction times as a function of measured quantum symbols (field quadratures [1]).

II. IMPACT OF FILTER FAILURES AND ATTACK

Failures can occur due to the use of a faulty filter or a malfunction within a filter such as manufacturing defects, degradation over time, or improper configuration, resulting in SFF or NBF. Fig. 1a describes the attack scenario where an eavesdropper applies a power splitting attack where an adversary extracts a portion of the QC signal before it is combined with CCs by mixing the QC with the CCs through

Fig. 1 (a) Attack scenario (d) Impact of faults and attacks on normal operation

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DWDM multiplexer (MUX). Fig. 1b shows the behavior of three conditions: (i) normal operation, (ii) fault, and (iii) attack. Both the fault condition and the eavesdropper attack degrade the value of secret key fraction (r) [1], which makes it challenging to distinguish between faults and attacks. These findings highlight the difficulty of accurately classifying the conditions based only on the values of r , requiring further investigation due to its relevance.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH: DESIGN AND INTEGRATION IN SDN-ENABLED CV-QKD

We consider a software defined networking (SDN)-enabled CV-QKD system. The details of such a network architecture can be found in [9]. For simplicity, this work refers to the complex controller architecture as *SDN control system* (Fig. 2), where it is proposed to integrate the designed approach for anomaly detection and classification. The QKD module is based on Gaussian-modulated coherent states (GMCS) CV-QKD protocol. The GMCS protocol is widely used in CV-QKD systems. It relies on coherent quantum states that are modulated using a bivariate Gaussian distribution, which is crucial for encoding the quantum information that is transmitted between two communicating parties Alice and Bob [1]. While the protocol comprises several steps, the *parameter estimation* is particularly relevant to the focus of this work. In this step, Alice and Bob reveal and compare a random subset of their field quadratures data (p_A, q_A) and (p_B, q_B). This comparison involves estimating the parameters of the QC such as excess noise and transmittance [1], that gives an estimated r in bits/symbols.

The proposed approach is stated in Fig. 3. It begins with the QKD Module performing the *parameter estimation*, during which an anomaly detection algorithm is employed to check for any anomalies (Fig. 2 point x). If an anomaly is detected, it is reported to the *SDN control system*. This controller utilizes a DNN (Fig. 2 point y) to classify the anomaly as either an attack or a fault. If it is an attack, it shuts down key-generation and raises an attack alarm. If it is a fault, the *SDN control system* checks if the fault is non-critical (which is confirmed by checking if the value of r is positive) and the key-generation continues. In this case, a non-critical fault alarm is raised for maintenance. Thus, shutdown and hence downtime of the QKD-module is avoided. Otherwise, the *SDN control system* halts key-generation (which is confirmed by checking if the value of r is negative), raises a critical fault alarm and declares it an inactive node.

Anomaly detection is designed by creating upper limits ($u.l$) and lower limits ($l.l$), crucial for distinguishing between normal and anomalous conditions. These limits are derived from the mean (μ) and variance (σ^2) of the values of r computed during normal operation. They are adjusted by a parameter γ to minimize false-negatives (anomaly detected as normal-operation) and false-positives (normal operation detected as anomaly). Specifically, the $u.l$ is $\mu + \gamma\sigma^2$ and the $l.l$ is $\mu - \gamma\sigma^2$. If during network operation r falls outside these bounds, an anomaly is detected.

DNN is designed to classify the anomaly as attacks and faults. It takes Bob's measured quadrature fields (p_B, q_B) data as input features for training and classification tasks. In network operation when anomalous data is fed into the DNN, it classifies the input as either an attack or a fault.

Fig. 2 Design and integration of the proposed approach

Fig. 3 Flowchart of the approach

IV. TEST SETUP AND RESULTS

The setup of CV-QKD in coexistence with classical DWDM channels is implemented using VPIphotonics [10] as shown in Fig. 4. This setup that introduces faults and attacks was previously validated experimentally in [3]. Given that the test setup was used in [3], the faults and attacks produced are expected to resemble practical implementations. In this test configuration (Fig. 4b), two nodes are considered: one at the Tx and one at the Rx.

The QKD module at the Tx (see Fig. 4a) generates GMCSs using a laser with a frequency of 193.2 THz and a 10-kHz linewidth. The laser carrier is modulated by an amplitude modulator (AM) and a phase modulator (PM), whereas a variable optical attenuator (VOA) at the Tx output adjusts the modulation variance (V_{mod}).

For the channel profile simulation, we use a full C-band scenario with 40 channels (39 CCs and 1 QC). This includes 39 unmodulated dummy CCs spanning from 192.1 THz to 193.1 THz (Channel (Ch) 21 to Ch 31 of the ITU-T grid) and from 193.3 THz to 196 THz (Ch 33 to Ch 60), which are combined with the QC at Ch 32 using a 100-GHz spaced DWDM MUX. These channels are transmitted through a 10-km standard single-mode fiber (SSMF). Fig. 4c shows the post-MUX optical spectrum with a power of -15 dBm per CC (0.91 dBm total launch power).

After transmission, the QC is separated using an optical rectangular bandpass filter (BPF) with a 10 GHz bandwidth and 40 dB stop-band attenuation. The QKD module at the receiver (Rx) (Fig. 4d) performs phase-diversity detection with a 90-degree optical hybrid and two pairs of balanced photodetectors, using a local oscillator (LO) derived from the Tx laser through a beam splitter (BS) [2]. A *parameter estimation* is carried out with an error reconciliation efficiency (β) of 0.95.

In Fig. 4b, the attacks are introduced before the MUX identified by the marker *Attack* and faults are introduced at

Fig. 4 (a) Detailed QKD module Tx, (b) Test configuration, (c) Optical Spectrum, and (d) Detailed QKD module Rx

Fig. 5 (a) Threshold optimization, (b) Accuracy, and (c) Prediction time

BPF identified as *Fault*. Four operational conditions are considered: normal operation, attack, SFF, and NBF. In normal operation, there is no SFF (0 GHz), the filter bandwidth is 12.5 GHz (flex grid scenario), and there is no attack loss (0 dB). For emulating Eve in attack scenario, a BS is used before the QC is multiplexed in the DWDM system. Three levels of attack-induced losses are evaluated: 1 dB, 2 dB, and 3 dB. In the SFF condition, three shifted filters are introduced with a frequency shift of: 5.95 GHz, 6.15 GHz, and 6.25 GHz relative to the central frequency of 193.2 THz. Lastly, in the NBF condition, three faulty filter bandwidths are considered: 0.4 GHz, 0.6 GHz, and 0.7 GHz[5].

For test and validation, first we acquire 100 samples for each possible cause of fault, attack, and normal operation case. We evaluate the anomaly detection strategy with $u.l$ and $l.l$. Fig. 5a illustrates the counts of false-positives and false-negatives for varying values of γ . As γ increases, false-positives decrease, whereas false-negatives remain unchanged. This suggests that optimizing $u.l$ and $l.l$ primarily impacts false-positives. At $\gamma = 1900$, false-positives become zero, identifying this value as the optimal threshold for detection.

Then we test classification strategy with DNN and GNB. An 80-20 % train-test split ratio is used to validate the classification algorithm. The DNN architecture consists of an input layer followed by three dense layers with ReLU activation and Dropout layers to prevent overfitting, ending in a softmax output layer for multi-class classification. The model is trained using categorical cross-entropy loss with the Adam optimizer. GNB was trained using the same dataset as DNN. We evaluated two parameters here, test accuracy and computational time of predictions (for an average of 1000 runs) with respect to the measured number of quantum symbols (N) at Rx taking as the input of DNN or GNB. The algorithms are run on 11th Gen Intel (R) Core (TM) i7-1165G7 @ 2.8GHz, 4 cores.

Fig. 5b and Fig. 5c present a comparative analysis of the performance of DNN and GNB classifiers based on accuracy and prediction time across varying N . In Fig. 5b, the GNB classifier maintains an accuracy of around 85%, showing minimal sensitivity to changes in N . In contrast, the DNN

classifier has a significant dependence on N , with its accuracy increasing as N grows, reaching optimal performance (100% accuracy) at $N=1024$. Fig. 5c highlights the trade-off in terms of prediction time. The DNN requires more computational time than GNB, with the prediction times increasing as N increases which is almost 4 times more than GNB at $N=1024$ (100% accuracy of DNN).

V. CONCLUSIONS

We propose an approach for detecting anomalies and classifying them as attacks and faults in CV-QKD copropagating in DWDM systems. It uses analytical methods for detection and DNN for classification to stop unnecessary system shutdowns and can be integrated into SDN-enabled CV-QKD. Results show that a simple classifier like GNB is inadequate for this task. A DNN is needed for accurate classification despite its 4 times longer prediction time.

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